

Population Studies on Obsessive Compulsive Disorder and Its Genetics as a Well-understood Disorder

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To cite this article: Dr. Arzu Özkan, Science, Volume 4, No. 8-5, 2022, p. 405 – 425. - 0099-0001-2209-0514.

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ISSN: 2667-9515

Barcode: 977266795001

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""The magazine will be at the subscriber's address in the first week of the month."" ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia") ("CURRENT SCIENCE") ("CURRENT SCIENCE") ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia") ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia") ("Scientific Studies – Current Science Georgia")

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Abstract

OCD, also known as obsessive compulsive disorder, is a quite common and persistent disorder. It is also strongly associated with disruption on a worldwide scale. The term "obsessive-compulsive and related disorders" refers to several diseases, the most prominent of which is OCD. In most cases, an inadequate diagnosis is followed by an inadequate treatment. In addition, obsessive-compulsive disorder (OCD) is an important example of neuropsychiatric disorder that contributes

to improved recognition, assessment, and outcomes, as well as individualized assessment of symptoms, degree of insight, and coverage of comorbidity. Psychotherapy on phenomenology, psychobiology, pharmacotherapy and psychotherapy was applied to OCD. OCD is featured by several neurobiological processes, some of which have been discovered, and specific brain circuits that contribute to OCD have also been uncovered. In addition, laboratory models have proved how cellular and molecular malfunction contributes to repetitive stereotypes, and the genetic makeup of obsessive-compulsive disorder (OCD) has become a well-understood disorder. Neurosurgery for patients with serotonin reuptake inhibitors and cognitive behavioral therapy for patients with persistent symptoms are effective treatments for obsessive-compulsive disorder (OCD). The combination of techniques focused on global mental health and translational research has the potential to both learn more about OCD and improve therapeutic outcomes. Some of the more common are obsessions and compulsions related to contamination along with washing or cleaning, concerns about harming themselves or others through control, mental rituals, aggressive or sexual thoughts or sexual thoughts, and symmetry, sorting or counting. Obsessions and compulsions in OCD patients. Other common obsessions and compulsions include fears of harming themselves or others through control. As part of our OCD research, we conducted a literature review and review.

Keywords: *OCD, Obsessive Compulsive Disorder, OCD Causes, OCD Outcomes, OCD Research*

1. Introduction

We use the term obsessive compulsive disorder to refer to the defining feature of hoarding disorder, which is the inability to get rid of things (OCD). For example, compulsive hoarding may be a symptom of obsessive -compulsive disorder (OCD). These symptom dimensions have been seen around the world, suggesting that in some respects OCD appears to be an apparently homogeneous condition. On the other hand, OCD may present with less typical symptoms such as impatience, obsessive jealousy, and preoccupation with music . 4-6. Another important feature of OCD is avoidance, in which patients limit their participation in various activities to avoid triggering their obsessions .

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OCD and other OCRDs , including cross-cutting comorbidities and family history , there are also fundamental differences in the biology, assessment, and treatment of each of these conditions. In addition, this Primer addresses OCD-related quality of life (QOL) concerns as well as related research topics.

At first, OCD was thought to be an extremely rare condition. On the other hand, the first rigorous population studies using operational criteria for the diagnosis of mental disorders have shown OCD to be one of the most common mental disorders and is estimated to be a significant contributor to the global burden of disease. These findings were published in the Journal of Affective Disorders. The lifetime prevalence of obsessive-compulsive disorder (OCD) has been confirmed by more recent nationally representative studies of between 2% and 3% and is associated with higher comorbidity and morbidity, although values differ between regions. Several sociodemographic correlations have been proved in epidemiological studies in which OCD or its symptoms are present. In the general population, obsessive -compulsive disorder is more common in women than men; however, the ratio of women to men with OCD in clinical samples is generally quite similar. Similarly, obsessive compulsive disorder can be seen in low-income, middle-income, and high-income countries and in people from all socioeconomic strata.

OCD usually develops at an early age and lasts for a significant period. The onset of obsessive - compulsive disorder (OCD) in women usually occurs during the teenage years. It is possible for some women to have OCD during the peripartum or postpartum periods. Age is the largest sociodemographic predictor of lifetime OCD , with the highest chance of onset between the ages of 18-29, which is consistent with the age at which OCD first appears in children and adolescents. On the other hand, those over 30 may experience a variety of onsets. While remission is possible for a significant percentage of people with obsessive-compulsive disorder (OCD) , longitudinal clinical and community studies have revealed that OCD symptoms can persist for decades.

OCD are consistent in both clinical and community samples. Obsessions and compulsions can be categorized into a small number of symptom dimensions , according to the findings of several

studies conducted in clinical settings . These dimensions include concerns about contamination (with next cleaning), concerns about damage (with next check), and concerns about symmetry (with next order). Studies in populations of various nationalities have shown that people with OCD have symptoms that fit a similar profile. While social and cultural factors can certainly influence the expression and experience of obsessive -compulsive symptoms, there is significant OCD symptom uniformity around the world (for example, contamination concerns may focus on syphilis in one region and HIV in others).

2. Coexistence of Morbidity and Comorbidity

OCD is distinguished by the presence of significant comorbidity. In the NCS-R, ninety percent of individuals with lifetime OCD (as decided by DSM-IV criteria) also met DSM-IV criteria for another lifetime disease. The most common of these disorders are anxiety disorders, mood disorders, impulse control disorders, and substance use disorders. Tic disorders and other obsessive -compulsive disorders often occur with OCD. OCD was approximately equally likely to start before or after a mood disorder, and impulse control and substance use were observed in 92.8% and 58.9% of cases, respectively. While OCD started after the accompanying anxiety disorders in 79.2% of the cases, it started after the accompanying anxiety disorders in only 58.9% of the cases. It started after the disorder¹⁴ was resolved. Additionally, there is some data to suggest that people with OCD are more likely to have a comorbidity of common medical conditions.

Obsessive -compulsive disorder, sometimes known as OCD, is a condition that affects a person's mental health and is characterized by unpleasant, intrusive, obsessive thoughts as well as repeated, compulsive actions, physically or mentally.

OCD affects about 2% of the total population. Symptoms usually present during childhood or adolescence, and it is quite unusual for this to develop after the age of 40. Obsessive-compulsive disorder (OCD), one of several diseases involving obsessive thoughts and compulsive activities , is classified as an anxiety disorder. OCD can have a significant impact on a person's quality of life and overall well-being.

3. What Exactly Is OCD?

An obsession or compulsion, distracting behavior, and repetitive thinking patterns are all hallmarks of the mental health illness known as OCD. Regularly accepted tasks can be challenging for a person suffering from OCD . Those who often suffer from OCD :

- *have mental processes such as visions or impulses that they believe they cannot manage.*
- *don't want to be bothered by these unwanted and invasive thoughts and feelings*
- *Suffers from great discomfort, which may be the result of fear, discontent, uncertainty, or belief that things should be done a certain way.*
- *Spends a significant amount of time focusing on these obsessions and indulging in compulsions that get in the way of daily tasks on a personal, social, and professional level.*
- *What exactly does the term "obsessive compulsive personality disorder" mean?*

In addition, this Primer addresses OCD-related quality of life (QOL) concerns as well as related research topics. On the other hand, the results of the first comprehensive population studies using operational criteria for the diagnosis of mental illness showed that OCD is one of the most common forms of mental illness. By some estimates, OCD manages a considerable proportion of the overall burden of disease worldwide¹². The lifetime prevalence of obsessive-compulsive disorder (OCD) has been confirmed by more recent nationally representative studies of between 2% and 3% and is associated with higher comorbidity and morbidity, although values vary between regions. Few sociodemographic links have been shown to exist in epidemiological studies of OCD or its symptomatology .

These relationships have been proven. In the general population, obsessive -compulsive disorder is more common in women than men; however, the ratio of women to men with OCD in clinical samples is generally quite similar. Similarly, obsessive compulsive disorder can be seen in low-income, middle-income, and high-income countries and in people from all socioeconomic strata. OCD usually develops at an early age and lasts for a significant period.

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some women to have OCD during the peripartum or postpartum periods. Age is the largest sociodemographic predictor of lifetime OCD, with the highest chance of onset between the ages of 18-29, which is consistent with the age at which OCD first appears in children and adolescents. However, people older than 30 can have many onsets of the condition. Longitudinal clinical and community studies have shown that although remission is possible in a considerable proportion of people with the disorder, OCD symptoms can persist for decades. Clinical manifestations of OCD are consistent in both clinical and community samples. Obsessions and compulsions can be subdivided into a small number of symptom dimensions, according to the findings of several studies conducted in clinical settings. These dimensions include concerns about contamination (at next cleaning), concerns about damage (at next check), and concerns about symmetry (at next order). Studies in populations of various nationalities have shown that people with OCD have symptoms that fit a similar profile. While social and cultural variables can certainly affect the expression and experience of obsessive-compulsive symptoms, there is a great deal of international uniformity in OCD symptoms (for example, contamination concerns may focus on syphilis in one place and HIV in another).

Coexistence of morbidity and comorbidity OCD is distinguished by the presence of significant comorbidity. In the NCS-R, ninety percent of individuals with lifetime OCD (as decided by DSM-IV criteria) also met DSM-IV criteria for another lifetime disease. The most common of these disorders are anxiety disorders, mood disorders, impulse control disorders, and substance use disorders¹⁴ (Figure 3). Tic disorders and other obsessive-compulsive disorders often occur with OCD. OCD was approximately equally likely to start before or after a mood disorder and started after comorbid impulse control and substance use disorders in 92.8% and 58.9% of cases, respectively.

While OCD started after the accompanying anxiety disorders in 79.2% of cases, the probability of onset before or after a mood disorder was approximately equal. There is also some data suggesting that those with OCD have a higher rate of comorbidity with other types of general medical illness.

4. What exactly is OCD?

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A mental health disorder known as obsessive-compulsive disorder (OCD) is characterized by stressful, destructive and intrusive obsessive thoughts as well as repetitive, compulsive behaviors. OCD affects about 2% of the total population. Symptoms usually present during childhood or adolescence, and it is quite unusual for this to develop after the age of 40. Obsessive-compulsive disorder (OCD), one of several diseases involving obsessive thoughts and compulsive activities, is classified as an anxiety disorder. OCD can have a significant impact on a person's quality of life and overall well-being.

An obsession or compulsion, distracting behavior, and repetitive thinking patterns are all hallmarks of the mental health illness known as OCD. Regularly accepted tasks can be challenging for a person suffering from OCD. OCD is characterized by the following symptoms in the individual: having thoughts, images, or impulses that the person believes they cannot control; not wanting to have these intrusive thoughts and feelings; experiencing a significant amount of discomfort, which may include fear, disgust, doubt, or the belief that something should happen. needs to be done in a certain way, spends a lot of time concentrating on these obsessions and develops compulsions that get in the way of personal, social and professional tasks.

5. What exactly is meant by the term "obsessive-compulsive personality disorder"?

The several types of OCD can have quite different effects on different individuals. It may consist of: Anxiety needs to be controlled Someone with OCD may feel like they need to check for mistakes over and over. This can include things like checking their bodies for signs of illness, verifying the authenticity of memories, repeatedly checking communications such as email. Other examples include checking faucets, alarms, door locks, home lights and appliances to prevent leakage, damage or fire; make mistakes; and controlling home appliances and lights. Anxiety about the spread of an illness Some people with OCD have an irresistible urge to shower or bathe all the time. They may worry that the things they touch are dirty or dangerous.

This can result in frequent brushing or hand washing; repeated cleaning of bathrooms, kitchens and other areas; avoiding crowds for fear of infection; and such.

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Some people have the impression that they are contaminated when they believe they have been mistreated or criticized by another person.

They can try to rid themselves of this feeling by washing their hands. This includes a person who has trouble getting rid of things that are no longer useful to them.

6. Intrusive Ideas and Reflections

This includes the feeling of being unable to keep unpleasant ideas running through one's head over and over. These may include acts of violence, such as injuring others or oneself, or even taking one's own life. Thoughts can cause significant discomfort to a person, but it is quite unusual for them to behave in a way that strongly reflects these thoughts. Although there is no evidence to support this belief, a person suffering from this type of OCD may be concerned that they are pedophiles. symmetry and conformity to a pattern A person suffering from this type of obsessive-compulsive disorder may need to arrange things in a certain order to avoid feeling uncomfortable or in danger. For example, they would regularly put books on a shelf in a certain order. OCD patients may have obsessions , compulsions, or both. These things have the potential to disturb a person and hinder their ability to conduct their regular activities. Below you can find more information about obsessions and compulsions. Obsessions While worrying is normal, people with OCD may find that their worries and fears take over their lives so much that even their most basic tasks cannot be done. The following are some of the most common motives for this anxiety: contaminants such as bodily fluids, germs, dirt and other elements Lack of control, such as fear of harming oneself or other people Perfectionism. Most individuals rely on ritual habits such as nighttime sleep routines to help them navigate their daily lives successfully . On the other hand, for a person suffering from OCD , the desire to engage in ritual behaviors is intense, frequent, and time-consuming. A ritualistic disposition can take over a person's behavior. Washing and cleaning, washing hands when necessary are examples of this. Early signs and symptoms Symptoms of obsessive-compulsive disorder often appear during adolescence, but this is not always the case. Complications that can occur in adolescents, including children with OCD , include:

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Poor self-esteem routines, problems completing the course, physical illness caused by stress, problems making or keeping friendships and other connections, etc. are all signs of stress.

There is some evidence that OCD is more common when it develops in infancy . On the other hand, men and women are equally affected after they reach maturity. Although experts are not sure what triggers OCD , several hypotheses have been put forward. Genetic, neurological, behavioral, cognitive, and environmental variables can all contribute. Genetic causes OCD appears to be inherited, suggesting there may be a genetic link, something experts are investigating. Imaging studies have led researchers to believe that the brains of patients with obsessive -compulsive disorder work in quite diverse ways. There is some evidence that certain genes, such as those that control how the brain responds to the neurotransmitter's dopamine and serotonin , play a role in the development of this condition. Children can get symptoms of obsessive -compulsive disorder (OCD) after exposure to certain illnesses, such as group A streptococcal infections, sore throat, or Lyme disease. H1N1 influenza virus The clinical manifestation of these OCD symptoms is occasionally referred to by mental health professionals as the pediatric acute onset neuropsychiatric syndrome (PANS). PANS presents with sudden-onset symptoms that reach their full intensity after 24 to 72 hours . They may disappear at some point in the future but reappear later. Behavioral causes One idea suggests that a person with OCD learns to avoid the fear associated with certain conditions or items by following rituals to reduce perceived risk .

Specifically, this theory suggests that a person learns to avoid fear associated with certain situations or objects. A period of severe stress, such as a terrible event or major loss, may be the trigger for one's first fear. OCD manifests as an increased tendency to avoid whatever a person fears after associating it with a particular thing or situation. People with a genetic predisposition to this condition may have a higher risk of experiencing it.

7. Cognitive Factors

Another explanation suggests that obsessive - compulsive disorder results from individuals misreading their own thoughts . Most people will experience unwanted or intrusive thoughts at

some point in their lives, but for those suffering from OCD , the importance of these thoughts may be exaggerated or excessive. It is possible for a person to reject these ideas most of the time; however, if thoughts persist, one may give them an undue value. A person suffering from OCD may have a false belief that the behavior they think will happen. They respond to threat or danger by taking aggressive and persistent measures to protect themselves . Environmental causes OCD can be triggered in people who are already predisposed to develop it because of genetics or another factor. A considerable number of patients reported that symptoms began to manifest within six months of stressful experiences such as birth problems during pregnancy or labor, intense conflict, acute illness, or traumatic brain injury. In some cases, people who suffer from OCD also have post- traumatic stress disorder , commonly known as PTSD .

8. Diagnosis

obsessions , compulsions, or both obsessions and compulsions that take a significant amount of time or cause significant distress or impairment in social, occupational, or other important settings is one of the criteria doctors look for when making a diagnosis . obsessive -compulsive disorder (OCD). OCD symptoms that are not better explained by another health condition Many added conditions, such as depression and anxiety, share symptoms with obsessive -compulsive disorder (OCD) and are often seen with OCD. OCD can be effectively treated in several ways. Appropriate course of action is decided by a person's symptoms , as well as by the extent to which these symptoms affect a person's life and general well-being.

The following are some options that are useful:

CBT stands for cognitive behavioral therapy. This type of psychotherapy, often called cognitive behavioral therapy (CBT), can help a person change the way they think, feel, and behave.

Exposure and response prevention (ERP), commonly known as cognitive therapy , is one possible therapy, along with other options.

ERP consists of:

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The individual is put into situations and events that could potentially cause them to experience fear and anxiety. Repetition of an anxiety-provoking experience can lead to a gradual reduction or complete disappearance of that experience through a psychological mechanism known as habituation. As a result of this reaction, the individual will learn to avoid compulsive behaviors. The first step in cognitive therapy is to get the individual to recognize and re-evaluate their ideas about the consequences of engaging in or avoiding obsessive behaviors.

Next, the therapist recommends that the individual look for evidence supporting the obsession as well as evidence not supporting the obsession. Find cognitive distortions associated with the obsession and try to develop a less dangerous response as an alternative to the intrusive thought, picture, or concept. The following are some suggestions for coping with OCD when exposed to the COVID-19 pandemic:

Medications OCD can be treated with a variety of different medications called selective serotonin reuptake inhibitors (SSRIs), which are a type of antidepressant.

Some examples are:

Escitalopram (Lexapro) fluvoxamine (Luvox) paroxetine (Paxil) fluoxetine (Prozac) sertraline (Zoloft) Unlike depression, obsessive compulsive disorder (OCD) treatment may require higher doses of medication.

However, it can accept to three months for a person to see any benefit. It is estimated that about half of all individuals with OCD do not respond to treatment with SSRIs alone ; therefore, doctors may also prescribe antipsychotic medications. Also in 2010, several researchers reported that CBT in combination with the tuberculosis drug D- cycloserine (Seromycin) may be an effective treatment for OCD. Additionally, it can help people with social anxiety. In the fifth edition of the Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders (DSM) published by the American Psychiatric Association (APA) in 2013, obsessive -compulsive disorder is under its own sub-category, “obsessive-compulsive and related disorders”. is in:

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“compulsive hoarding” and “over-hoarding” Obsessive compulsive disorder (OCD) Body dysmorphic disorder, also known as BDD (BDD) Hoarding disorder Trichotillomania Disorder characterized by plucking or picking

Obsessive -compulsive disorder and similar conditions may develop because of another medical problem . Associated with obsessive-compulsive behavior, but not specifically defined as such A. Presence of compulsive behaviors, obsessions, or both: Obsessions are distinguished by two features:

first , inconvenience is not welcome; Second, the discomfort creates significant discomfort for most people. The person tries to refocus their attention on something else to suppress unwanted thoughts, impulses, or images (i.e., by replacing them with a compulsion).

Two points that characterize compulsions are:

Behaviors or mental activities Persistent preoccupation with an obsession because of feeling compelled to do so.

In addition, this Primer addresses OCD-related quality of life (QOL) concerns as well as related research topics. Go to: Epidemiology Prevalence and demography At first, OCD was thought to be an exceedingly rare condition. On the other hand, the first rigorous population studies using operational criteria for the diagnosis of mental disorders have shown OCD to be one of the most common mental disorders and is estimated to be a significant contributor to the global burden of disease. These findings were published in the Journal of Affective Disorders. The lifetime prevalence of obsessive-compulsive disorder (OCD) has been confirmed by more recent nationally representative studies of between 2% and 3% and is associated with higher comorbidity and morbidity, although values vary between regions. Few sociodemographic links have been shown to exist in epidemiological studies of OCD or its symptomatology . These relationships have been proven. In the general population, obsessive -compulsive disorder is more common in women than men; however, the ratio of women to men with OCD in clinical samples is generally quite similar. Similarly, obsessive compulsive disorder can be seen in low-income, middle-income, and high-income countries and in people from all socioeconomic strata. OCD usually develops at an early

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age and lasts for a significant period. Nearly one in four men started smoking before the age of 1014 , according to the National Comorbidity Study Review (NCS-R) findings . The onset of obsessive -compulsive disorder (OCD) in women usually occurs during the teenage years. It is possible for some women to have OCD during the peripartum or postpartum periods.

the largest sociodemographic predictor of lifetime OCD , with the highest chance of onset between the ages of 18-2914, which is consistent with the age at which OCD first appears in children and adolescents. However, people older than 30 can have many onsets of the condition. Longitudinal clinical and community studies have shown that although remission is possible in a considerable proportion of people with the disorder, OCD symptoms can persist for decades. Clinical manifestations of OCD are consistent in both clinical and community samples. Obsessions and compulsions can be subdivided into a small number of symptom dimensions , according to the findings of several studies conducted in clinical settings . These dimensions include concerns about contamination (at next cleaning), concerns about damage (at next check), and concerns about symmetry (at next order).

9. OCD Patients Have Symptoms That Fit A Similar Profile

Studies in populations of various nationalities have shown that OCD patients have symptoms that fit a similar profile^{13,14}. While social and cultural variables can certainly affect the expression and experience of obsessive -compulsive symptoms, there is a great deal of international uniformity in OCD symptoms (for example, contamination concerns may focus on syphilis in one place and HIV in another). Coexistence of morbidity and comorbidity OCD is distinguished by the presence of significant comorbidity. In the NCS-R, ninety percent of individuals with lifetime OCD (as decided by DSM-IV criteria) also met DSM-IV criteria for another lifetime disease. The most common of these disorders are anxiety disorders, mood disorders, impulse control disorders, and substance use disorders¹⁴ (Figure 3). Tic disorders and other obsessive -compulsive disorders often occur with OCD. OCD was approximately equally likely to start before or after a mood disorder and started after comorbid impulse control and substance use disorders in 92.8% and 58.9% of cases, respectively . While OCD started after the accompanying anxiety disorders in

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79.2% of cases, the probability of onset before or after a mood disorder was approximately equal. Additionally, there is some data to suggest that those with OCD are more likely to have comorbidities with other types of general medical disorders.

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10. What exactly is meant by the term "obsessive-compulsive personality disorder"?

The several types of OCD can have quite different effects on different individuals. It may consist of: Anxiety needs to be controlled Someone with OCD may feel like they need to check for mistakes over and over. This can include things like checking their bodies for signs of illness, verifying the authenticity of memories, repeatedly checking communications such as email. Other examples include checking faucets, alarms, door locks, home lights and appliances to prevent leakage, damage or fire; make mistakes ; and controlling home appliances and lights. Anxiety about the spread of an illness Some people with OCD have an irresistible urge to shower or bathe all the time. They may worry that the things they touch are dirty or dangerous. Some people have the impression that they are contaminated when they believe they have been mistreated or criticized by another person. They can try to rid themselves of this feeling by washing their hands. Hoarding This involves a person struggling to get rid of things that are no longer useful to them. Intrusive ideas and brooding This includes the feeling of being unable to keep unpleasant ideas running through one's head over and over. These may include acts of violence, such as injuring others or oneself, or even taking one's own life. Thoughts can cause significant discomfort to a person, but it is quite unusual for them to behave in a way that strongly reflects these thoughts.

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Although there is no evidence to support this belief, a person suffering from this type of OCD may be concerned that they are pedophiles. symmetry and conformity to a pattern A person suffering from this type of obsessive - compulsive disorder may need to arrange things in a certain order to avoid feeling uncomfortable or in danger.

11. Conclusion

Consider a person who takes care of a baby when they are under a lot of stress and inadvertently gets the idea that they must harm the child. It is possible for a person to reject these ideas most of the time; however, if thoughts persist, one may give them an undue value. A person suffering from OCD may have a false belief that the behavior they think will happen. They respond to threat or danger by taking aggressive and persistent measures to protect themselves . Environmental causes OCD can be triggered in people who are already predisposed to develop it because of genetics or another factor. A considerable number of patients reported that symptoms began to manifest within six months of stressful experiences such as birth problems during pregnancy or labor, intense conflict, acute illness, or traumatic brain injury. In some cases, people who suffer from OCD also have post- traumatic stress disorder , commonly known as PTSD . Diagnosis The presence of obsessions , compulsions, or both obsessions and compulsions that take a significant amount of time or cause significant distress or impairment in social, occupational, or other important settings is one of the criteria doctors look for when making a diagnosis. obsessive -compulsive disorder (OCD). OCD symptoms that are not better explained by another health condition Many added conditions, such as depression and anxiety, share symptoms with obsessive -compulsive disorder (OCD) and are often seen with OCD. Treatment OCD can be effectively treated in several ways. Appropriate course of action is decided by a person's symptoms , as well as by the extent to which these symptoms affect a person's life and general well-being. The following are some useful options: CBT stands for cognitive behavioral therapy. This type of psychotherapy, often called cognitive behavioral therapy (CBT), can help a person change the way they think, feel, and behave. Exposure and response prevention (ERP), commonly known as cognitive therapy , is one possible therapy, along with other options. ERP consists of: The individual is put into circumstances and

events that could potentially cause them to experience fear and anxiety. Repetition of an anxiety-provoking experience can lead to a gradual reduction or complete disappearance of that experience through a psychological mechanism known as habituation. As a result of this reaction, the individual will learn how to avoid taking part in obsessive behaviors. The first step in cognitive therapy is to get the individual to recognize and re-evaluate their ideas about the consequences of engaging in or avoiding obsessive behaviors. The person tries to refocus their attention on something else (that is, by replacing them with a compulsion) to suppress unwanted ideas, impulses, or visions .

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